

Stepwise Stability Constants of Gallium(III) Complexes with Picolinic Acid and 8-Hydroxyquinoline and its Derivatives

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Manuscript received 5 August 1974; revised 10 December 1974; accepted 13 January 1975

The potentiometric study of Gallium(III) complexes with Picolinic acid (PA), 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonic acid (OSA), 7-iodo-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonic acid (IOSA) in aqueous medium and with 8-Hydroxyquinoline (OX) in 50% v/v aqueous-dioxan media have been carried out at an ionic strength $\mu = 0.2M$. The Proton-Ligand stability constants and stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving-Rossotti. Log K values have been computed by alternative methods. The trend in stability constant values of Gallium(III) complexes have been found to be $OX > OSA > IOSA > PA$.

THE paper describes the stepwise complex formation of Gallium(III) with (a) Picolinic acid (PA), (b) 8-Hydroxyquinoline (OX), (c) 8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonic acid (OSA) and (d) 7-iodo-8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulfonic acid (IOSA) by potentiometric method. Reactions of Ga(III) with (b) and (d) have however earlier been reported using spectrophotometric method¹. The ligands have been chosen in such a way that effect of donor atoms on stability of complexes may be studied by the addition of various substituent groups.

"Practical" proton-ligand stability constants of ligands and metal-ligand stability constants (stepwise) have been obtained by Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti².

Experimental

Solutions: A stock solution (0.01208M) of $Ga(NO_3)_3 \cdot 8H_2O$ (Fluka) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid to prevent the hydrolysis. The metal content was estimated gravimetrically by precipitation of Gallium as 8-Hydroxyquinolinolate and also by titration of Gallium with EDTA. Stock solutions, 0.05M of PA (Sigma), 0.0025M OSA (E. Merck) and 0.005M IOSA (B.D.H.) were prepared by dissolving requisite quantities in doubly distilled water. 0.015M OX (B.D.H.) was prepared by dissolving requisite quantity in purified³ dioxan. All these solutions were standardised potentiometrically. Solution of carbon dioxide free sodium hydroxide (Merck) and 0.1M perchloric acid (Riedel) was prepared and standardised potentiometrically. Stock solution of sodium perchlorate (neutral) was prepared by dissolving Analar sample of $NaClO_4 \cdot H_2O$ (Riedel) in double distilled water.

Apparatus: A pH-meter (Beckman model H-2) with glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to determine change in hydrogen ion concentration of

the solutions using KNO_3 (sat.) salt bridge. Thermostat (U-10 model, made in Germany) was used to maintain the temperature of solution with $\pm 0.02^\circ$ accuracy. The design of the cell was such that it allowed nitrogen to be passed through the solution and enabled measurements to be carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

Procedure: Three mixtures were prepared in case of PA and OX as follows: A: $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ perchloric acid; B: $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ perchloric acid + $5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand; C: $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ perchloric acid + $5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand + $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ metal solution. The three mixtures were prepared in case of OSA and IOSA as follows: A: $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ perchloric acid; B: $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ perchloric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand; C: $2.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ perchloric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ ligand + $4.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ metal solution. Concentrations of common ingredients were kept identical in different cases. Total volume was made 100 ml in case of PA, OSA and IOSA by using double distilled water. In case of OX, dioxan was used to adjust the total volume to 75 ml, so that the dioxan in mixture was 50% v/v. An appropriate amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added to maintain ionic strength 0.2 in all the cases. The ratio between the metal salt and the ligands was 1:5. The difference in the amount of sodium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations is a measure of extent of complexation. A graph between pH and volume of alkali required for the corresponding changes was plotted. The three titration curves obtained were referred to as: (A) acid titration curve, (B) ligand titration curve, (C) complex titration curve.

Methods: To calculate the formation constants of proton-ligand system, the $\bar{n}_A$ at different pH values were calculated. In case of mixed solvent system (OX) the pH-meter reading (B_1) was taken into consideration² for calculation of $\bar{n}_A$. Two methods were used: (a) Interpolation at half $\bar{n}_A$ values, (b) Interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ values.

The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pL using four different methods, (a) Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, (b) Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values, (c) Least squares method, (d) Elimination method.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constants: The formation curves were extended between 0 to 1 for PA and 0 to 2 for OSA and IOSA in $\bar{n}_A$ scale indicating dissociation of H_2PA^+ , H_3OSA^+ , H_3IOSA^+ as follows

The formation curve for OX was drawn between $\bar{n}_A$ and pH-meter reading (B) and was extended between 0 to 2 in the $\bar{n}_A$ scale showing the dissociation of H_2OX^+ as follows

The values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ at 25° temperature for all the ligands as obtained by method (b) of interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ values are summarised in the Table 1. $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ have error limits of ± 0.03 and ± 0.05 respectively.

Metal-ligand stability constants: The titration curves (B and C) in all the cases have been found to converge above pH 5.0 indicating that the complexation is complete below this pH. It may however be mentioned that in case of PA these two curves again diverge after pH 5.0 indicating the liberation of extra protons due to hydrolysis of complex. Considering above points and to avoid any possible error

in $\bar{n}$ values were calculated only upto pH 3.0 in all the cases except OX where the calculations were done upto pH 3.8. In case of PA, $\bar{n}$ values were found to extend from 0 to 2.7. In case of OSA and IOSA $\bar{n}$ values were extended from 0 to 2.9 whereas in oxine it extends from 1 to 3.0 indicating that first complex has formed below the pH 2.0.

As mentioned before the stability constant values were calculated using various computational methods and the table includes the results obtained by best suitable method for the particular cases in question. It may however be mentioned that in case of OX where the first complex was forming at lower pH, the elimination method was used to obtain its value as reported in the table. The error limits in case of $\log K_1$ is ± 0.05 and $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ as ± 0.07 respectively.

It is observed from the stability data that the complexes of Gallium(III) with PA are quite stable. In case of OX and its derivatives the trend in stability of complexes is in the order.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE PROTON—LIGAND AND METAL—LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS

* = 50% dioxan

Protonation Constants of the ligands at 25° ($\mu = 0.2M$)			Metal-ligand stability constant at 25° ($\mu = 0.2M$)		
Ligand	Constants	Value	Complex	Constants	Value
PA	$\log K_1^H$	5.23	Ga(III)-PA	$\log K_1(c)$	5.51
				$\log K_2(b)$	5.37
		$\log K_3(a)$		4.77	
		$\log \beta$		15.65	
OX*	$\log K_1^H$	10.67	Ga(III)-OX*	$\log K_1(d)$	13.64
	$\log K_2^H$	4.63		$\log K_2(a)$	12.95
	$\log \beta^H$	15.30		$\log K_3(a)$	11.05
		$\log \beta$		37.64	
OSA	$\log K_1^H$	8.47	Ga(III)-OSA	$\log K_1(c)$	10.55
	$\log K_2^H$	3.82		$\log K_2(b)$	9.40
	$\log \beta^H$	12.29		$\log K_3(a)$	8.79
		$\log \beta$		28.74	
IOSA	$\log K_1^H$	6.85	Ga(III)-IOSA	$\log K_1(c)$	8.36
	$\log K_2^H$	2.39		$\log K_2(b)$	8.06
	$\log \beta^H$	9.24		$\log K_3(a)$	7.88
		$\log \beta$		24.30	

$\log K_1^H = \pm 0.03$; $K_2^H = \pm 0.05$

$\log K_1 = \pm 0.05$; $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3 = \pm 0.07$.

(a) = Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, (b) = Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values, (c) = Least squares method, (d) = Elimination method.

which is in order of decreasing basicity. The substitution of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group and further addition of Iodo group in parent OX analogue decreases the stability of complexes which is due to electron withdrawing properties of these added groups.

Acknowledgement

We thank Prof. R. H. Sahasrabudhey, Nagpur University, Nagpur, for providing facilities.

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